

Infographic #3

EEG and ECoG Placement and Reading of 10-20 System

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EEG and ECoGs Placement & Readings of 10-20 System

Brain Waves and States

Delta Waves 0 – 4 Hz

1. Not present in an alert individual
2. Present in stage 3 & 4 sleep
3. Pathological problem if seen in an awake patient

Alpha Waves 8 – 12 Hz

1. Prominent when eyes are closed
2. Seen in occipital lobe
3. Large sinusoidal waves approximately 50 uV

Theta Waves 4 – 8 Hz

1. Prominent in drowsiness
2. Present in stage 3 & 4 sleep
3. Pathological problem if seen in an awake patient

Beta Waves 12 – 30 Hz

1. Prominent when eyes are open
2. High frequency waves
3. Present while patient is awake and alert
4. Formed in the frontal lobe

Class Notes Fundamentals of EEG & ECoG ACN 7372 – HCS 7372 Seminar in Neuroscience

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